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Transformational Leadership Style And Organizational Performance Of Telecommunication Companies In South-West, Nigeria

ODUNOLA Ezekiel

Department of Management

Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Portharcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of transformational leadership style on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in the South-West, Nigeria. The findings showed that the study revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria, as indicated by the highest weighted mean score of 4.05 and $r = 0.667$. This implies that adequate adoption of transformational leadership style in terms of inspiration vision, idealized influence, individual consideration, and intellectual stimulation brings about a corresponding improvement of organisational performance measured by service quality. The study concluded that the transformational leadership style serves as a yardstick for assessing organizational performance measured by the quality of service delivery. The study recommended that management of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria should ensure the effective implementation of leadership style that has the potential of improving service quality as the life of organisation in the face of stiff competition in meeting its desired performance.

Keywords: Transformational leadership, quality service delivery, companies

INTRODUCTION

The telecommunications industry stands as a dynamic and integral part of the global economy, driving connectivity and communication across the globe (Shadi et al., 2018). As the demand for seamless and advanced communication services continues to surge, telecommunication companies find themselves navigating a complex landscape where organisational performance plays a pivotal role in determining success and competitiveness. The effectiveness of these companies is shaped not only by the quality of their services and technological innovations but also by the intricacies of their organisational structures, leadership styles, and strategic decision-making processes. As telecommunications companies strive to meet the increasing expectations of consumers and grapple with rapid technological advancements, understanding the dynamics of organisational performance becomes paramount for achieving long-term viability and leadership in the telecommunications landscape (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014).

Thus, organisational performance refers to the extent to which a telecommunication companies achieves its stated objectives and goals through improvement in market share, profitability and service quality. It encompasses the overall effectiveness, efficiency, and success of an organisation in utilizing its resources to deliver desired outcomes. Improved organisational performance is crucial for telecommunication firms due to various factors that impact the industry's competitiveness, sustainability, and ability to meet the

evolving demands of the market (Rowold, 2011). The telecommunications industry is highly competitive. Improved organisational performance enables firms to stay competitive by adopting cutting-edge technologies, offering innovative services, and responding swiftly to market changes. Improved organisational performance in telecommunication firms is essential for maintaining a competitive edge, meeting customer expectations, adapting to technological advancements, and sustaining long-term growth. Firms that prioritize and achieve improved performance are better positioned to thrive in the dynamic and ever-evolving telecommunications industry. This work measures organisational performance in terms of service quality, profitability and market share.

The telecommunications industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with the advent of new technologies and increased competition. This has put pressure on telecommunication companies to improve their service quality in order to retain customers and stay competitive. As consumers increasingly rely on telecommunications for both personal and professional needs, the quality of services offered by telecommunications providers has emerged as a critical factor influencing customer loyalty, market competitiveness, and overall industry sustainability (Bill, 2018). Service quality refers to the extent to which a service rendered by telecommunication companies meets or exceeds customer expectations. The ability of the service provider to consistently deliver accurate, dependable, and error-free services as promised talk more about their performance. The uniformity and reliability of service delivery across different channels, locations, and over time, ensuring a consistent customer experience seems to be another cardinal factor. Achieving high service quality is essential for building customer loyalty, positive word-of-mouth, and maintaining a competitive edge in the marketplace. Service quality is particularly critical in service-oriented industries like telecommunications, where the intangible nature of the product places a premium on the overall customer experience (Jahan, 2019).

In the realm of leadership theories, transformational leadership stands out as a powerful and influential approach that has garnered attention for its ability to inspire and elevate organisational performance. Rooted in the idea of leaders as visionary catalysts for positive change, transformational leadership goes beyond traditional management practices (AbdulRahman et al, 2021). Transformational leadership is a leadership style that focuses on inspiring and motivating followers to achieve exceptional performance and personal growth. Transformational leaders articulate a compelling vision of the future, inspiring others to share in the pursuit of common goals. They paint a vivid picture of what success looks like and instill a sense of purpose and direction. Makambe and Gaone (2020) asserted that transformational leaders encourage creativity and innovation by challenging the status quo and fostering an environment of intellectual stimulation. They promote critical thinking and open dialogue. Transformational leadership stands as a beacon of inspiration and empowerment within the leadership landscape. By combining visionary thinking, charismatic influence, and a focus on individual and collective growth, transformational leaders have the potential to create transformative change, elevate organisational performance, and leave a lasting legacy of positive impact. A well-designed structure aligns with the organisation's strategic goals, enhances operational efficiency, and contributes to overall performance.

Background to the study

The transmission of media is recognized as a hallmark and important component of the digital organisation (Clement, 2015; Wendy, 2020). It appears that customers continue to complain about poor services organisation rendered which manifests through dropped calls, high-rate calls cost, network failure and information membership use, these alone has been revealed to have hampered the success and performance of organisation in terms of poor service deliver. It equally seems that some of the low-quality services recently mentioned, such as voice and information management are underpinning consumers' and unique beneficiaries' demands. All of these inadequacies are recurring problems that hinder these firms' progress (Daud 2016). For example, inspirations, education, and task preparation may empower workers to perform at their best. This demonstrates that there is a lot of regulatory competence and limitations that need to be put up or comprehended.

To this end, it is necessary to ask the leadership styles practiced in these organisation. We do not know the level of adoption of appropriate transformational leadership style in enhancing performance of organisation in terms of service quality. Another issue that necessitated this study is the fact that there appears to be a dearth of empirical studies on how leadership style interacts with organisational performance within the context of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria. Although, there has been several research efforts that spur the relationship between variables understudy, for instance, AbdulRalman et al, (2021) examined the influence of transformational leadership on organisational performance in Indonesia; Singh et al. (2021) investigated the transactional and transformational leadership styles as predictors of employee performance during the covid-19 crisis and the mediating role of organisational culture of private sector in Kajarta, Indonesia. John (2019) examined the influence of leadership styles on organisational performance at Tamakavi development association, North region of Ghana; Makara (2019) investigated the impact of leadership styles on organisational performance at Beltel international university; Makambe and Gaone (2020) examined the effects of leadership styles on employee's performance of a selected commercial bank in Bostwana; Ethelmary and Anthony (2020) examined the influence of leadership styles on performance of foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State;

Despite the attempts of the studies aforementioned, none was able to empirically examined the relationship between transformational leadership style and organisational performance of Telecommunication Companies specifically in South West, Nigeria. The current study examined the transformational leadership style (inspiration vision, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence and individual consideration. Organisational performance is measured in the current work in terms of service quality (customer satisfaction, service reliability and service consistency. The current study also adopted structure as the organisational factor. Even few of the studies that share the same dimension, measures and indicators, are not presented as used in this study. Therefore, there is need to close this gap

The study was to examine the relationship between transformational leadership style and organisational performance of telecommunication companies in South West, Nigeria. In view of the above stated objectives, the following research questions have been postulate. What is the relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of telecommunication companies in South West, Nigeria?

The significance of this study can be adjudged in terms of its potential benefits to the following category of information users: Managers and social scientists who their paramount is to assess how different leadership styles affect the telecommunication sector. The study hopes that the findings of this research will act as a guideline for company managers and policymakers to improve their leadership style for the telecommunication sectors and overall success.

RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Transformational Leadership Style

The term transformational leadership was coined by Downton in his book *Rebel Leadership: Commitment and Charisma in a Revolutionary Process* in 1973. When it comes to leadership, transformational leadership has been proposed by Burns and extended by Bass and associates as an alternative to the trait, style, contingency or exchange models. The idealized influence, inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration of the transformational style of leadership has been widely recommended as the best way to manage change. Transformative behaviors are more prevalent in the followers of leaders who score highly on the transformational leadership factors identified by (Bass, et al. 1987). Transformative leadership aims to change people and organisations in a literal sense to expand their vision, insight, and understanding; clarify their purpose in life; and bring about changes that are long-lasting, self-perpetuating and momentum building." One of the first chapters of James McGregor Burns' political leadership book, "*Transformational Leadership*," focused on this concept. Contrasts between transformational and transactional leadership are made by him (Yukl, 2014).

According to Bass (1985), a transformational leader's behaviour originates in the personal values and beliefs of the leader and motivates subordinates to do more than expected (Obiwuru et al., 2011). Transformational leadership style focuses on developing the followers and considering their needs. Managers that concentrate on transformational leadership focuses mainly on developing the general value system of the employees such as development of skills, motivation level and moralities (Ebrahim, 2018). Individuals and social systems are transformed as a result of leaders who use transformational leadership techniques. As a result, these methods can lead to positive changes in followers that could serve as models for future leaders. Transformational leadership also appeals to the employees' moral values. People's awareness and motivation to effect change in institutions will rise as a result of this (Yukl, 2014). Leaders who use transformational leadership will gain the respect and loyalty of their followers. Leaders who are transformational inspire their followers to go above and beyond their initial expectations. When it comes to inspiring employee motivation and articulating an inspiring vision, transformational leadership involves internalization (Yukl (2014). Other than that, transformational leadership inspires their followers, and as a result, their followers tend to imitate and espouse their leaders' attributes.

Conceptually, transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems. Regardless, transformational leadership is an effective leadership style in the global arena because it is the leadership that is desired by the followers, if not we could say that it is the prototype of leadership that employees want. Transformative leadership has an impact on all social levels, regardless of cultural differences, because it transcends the leader's positive personal interests into a common good for the followers (Burns, 1978 in Yukl, 2014). According to Yukl (2014), leaders can transform their followers in three ways, by making them more aware of the importance of the task outcome; by instilling a sense of purpose in them and by activating their higher order of needs.

In transformational leadership, the subordinates trust, admire and give absolute respect and loyalty to the leaders. Moreover, they are motivated to do more than what was initially expended to do (Obiwuru et al., 2011; Bass 1985). The transformational leader then motivates the subordinates by making them initially aware of significance of task outcomes, implementing them to transcend their own self-interest for the sake of the organisation and activating their higher order needs. According to Bass and Avolio (1994), the leader encourages the followers to think critically and seek new ways to approach their jobs, resulting in intellectual stimulation. Podsakoff et al. (1996), opined that there is an increase in the level of performance, satisfaction and commitment to the goals of an organisation, as a result of transformational leadership style. Transformational leaders move followers beyond the immediate self-interest (Bass, 1999). Transformational leadership creates an environment in which employees are motivated and energized (Dejang & Bruch, 2013).

Inspirational Vision: Kouzes and Posner (2007), Leaders provide an inspirational vision by envisioning a better future, communicating that vision to their constituents, and then, by their words and deeds, bringing that vision to life for themselves and others. Avolio and Yammarino (2002), Inspirational leaders challenge followers' existing beliefs, values, and expectations to promote creative thinking and new perspectives. They engage followers' hearts and minds in a shared vision that evokes passion and commitment. Inspirational vision leadership is characterized by a leader's capability to communicate a clear and motivating vision that resonates with followers' values and aspirations, fostering enthusiasm and commitment (Avolio & Bass, 1988).

Inspirational vision leadership refers to a leader's skill in creating and communicating an inspiring and compelling vision that stimulates followers to transcend their current limitations and achieve extraordinary results (Kouzes & Posner, 1995).

Inspirational vision leadership involves the ability to convey a clear and motivating picture of an ideal future, fostering enthusiasm and commitment among followers, thereby influencing their actions and decisions (Northouse, 2013). Inspirational vision leadership refers to the art of envisioning a compelling future state, effectively communicating it to others, and igniting passion and determination to transform that vision into reality (Mendenhall & Osland, 2018).

Intellectual Stimulation: Bass and Riggio (2006), Intellectual stimulation refers to the leader's ability to stimulate followers to be creative and to challenge their own beliefs and values. Transformational leaders encourage followers to think independently and to explore new ideas. Intellectual stimulation leadership fosters an environment where followers are encouraged to challenge assumptions, explore diverse perspectives, and engage in constructive debates to arrive at innovative solutions (James, 1978). Intellectual stimulation leadership involves leaders who inspire and challenge their followers to question established norms, engage in continuous learning, and strive for intellectual growth (Warren, 1989). Intellectual stimulation leadership encourages followers to explore beyond their comfort zones, fostering an environment that values innovative thinking and intellectual curiosity (Ronald, 2017). Intellectual stimulation leadership refers to the leader's ability to provoke thoughtful discussions, challenge preconceived notions, and inspire followers to think critically and creatively (Charalambos, 2018). Intellectual stimulation leadership entails leaders who create an atmosphere of intellectual curiosity, where followers are empowered to generate innovative ideas, solve complex problems, and continuously improve (Bassam, 2009).

Idealized Influence: Bernard and Bruce (1994), idealized influence refers to a leader's ability to be a charismatic role model who gains the admiration, trust, and respect of followers through personal example and moral character. Burns (1978) opined that idealized influence involves a leader's capability to instill a sense of purpose and inspire followers by demonstrating high ethical standards and a commitment to shared values. Bass and Riggio (2006), idealized influence signifies a leader's capacity to create a sense of vision and mission, gaining follower commitment by showcasing qualities such as integrity, consistency, and a willingness to take risks for the greater good.

Barbuto and Wheeler (2006), idealized influence refers to a leader's demonstration of authentic and transparent behavior that cultivates trust, belief, and follower identification with the leader's vision and values. Bass (1985), idealized influence involves a leader's ability to act as a role model by displaying moral and ethical behavior, promoting a sense of collective identity, and fostering admiration and respect among followers. Howell and Avolio (1992), idealized influence entails a leader's ability to create a positive and aspirational image that encourages followers to view the leader as a symbol of inspiration, leading to increased trust, loyalty, and identification with the leader's ideals. Bass & Riggio (2006): Idealized influence is "the degree to which a leader's behavior is perceived as a role model for followers, who respect and trust the leader and who identify with and emulate the leader" (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Avolio and Bass (1991), idealized influence is "the charismatic attributes that create strong role model qualities and, in essence, raise followers' identification with the leader from transactional to transformational levels. Shamir et al. (1993), idealized influence is "the process by which leaders generate perceptions of their 'charismatic' behavior and are able to foster the admiration, trust, and respect of their followers.

Individual Consideration: Individual consideration is defined as the consideration of employee's individuality. Transformational leaders link priorities of every follower with the development of the organisation (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Leaders focus on the development and training of employees that creates promotion opportunities (Avolio et al., 2004). The outcomes of these characteristic depend on the ability of the leader to stimulate and direct followers in order to achieve desired outcome (Avolio et al., 2004; Snell et al., 2013). Individual consideration is the inclusion of people into the transformation process of an organisation (Simic, 2014). The leader who is aware of different needs and wishes of people has an opportunity to use all those different demands in the right way (Conger, 2014).

Individual consideration constitutes developing followers through coaching, mentoring and teaching are the central indicator of the transformational leadership style (Kirkbride, 2006; Hoffman & Frotst, 2006; Sarros & Santora, 2001). The individualized consideration leader demonstrates high concern for their followers, treats them as individuals and gets to know well about them and listens to both their concerns and ideas (Kirkbride, 2006; Offman & Frotst, 2006; Sarros & Santora, 2001).

Organisational Performance

The concept of organisational performance is well thought-out to be the sum of accomplishments that has been achieved by all departments. It is the organisational goals that have been set in a given period of time to outline its accomplishments that are involved in each stage. The idea of organisational performance is affiliated to the survival and success of an organisation (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). Organisational performance is a multidimensional construct that consists of four elements - customer-focused performance, including customer satisfaction, and product or service performance; financial and market performance, including revenue, profits, market position, cash-to-cash cycle time, and earnings per share; human resource performance, including employee organisational effectiveness, including time to market, level of innovation, and production and supply chain flexibility (Alam, 2013). In order to achieve the desired level of financial performance, many organisations have restructured, and implemented total quality management programmes and introduced competitive staff benefits. Despite such attempts, many organisations have not achieved the anticipated results or have not experienced high performance. Analyses of the sustained superior financial performance of certain American organisations have attributed their success to the specific cultures of the respective organisations (Zheng & McLean, 2010). Organisational performance includes effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, quality, and innovation. For the purpose of this study, organisational performance could be measured through service quality.

Therefore, Service Quality refers to an appeal to promote rising standards. Thus, measures of job quality, quality of work or quality of employment should not simply provide researchers with an existing overview of the employment situation, but also allow for an evaluation of the conditions uncovered. While conceptualizations vary within the social sciences, psychologists tend to focus on non-economic work factors such as intrinsically meaningful or challenging work, and in particular on the “goodness” of work when considering job quality (Cox et al. in Barling et al., 2009). Quality represents the ongoing process of building and sustaining relationships by assessing, anticipating setting standard, and fulfilling stated and implied needs. Quality means that the organisation's culture is defined by and supports the constant attainment of customer satisfaction through an integrated system of tools, techniques, and training (Sashkin & Kiser 2013). Furthermore, a manager who is deeply concerned on work quality might choose to initiate principle in terms of losses to reduce the tendency of loss averse employees to concentrate on quantity rather than quality. Work quality is a management technique used to communicate to workers what is required to produce, the desired quality of products and services and to influence worker actions to complete tasks according to the quality specifications. According to Akin and Hopelain in Jahan (2019), defined work quality as the key elements such as right types of human resources, identification with the job, teamwork, trust and support, status determined by knowledge of job and performance, support for accomplishment and autonomous use of skills. Service quality is defined as a comparison of customer expectations with service performance. The organisations with high service quality meet the customer needs and also remain economical in terms of competition as improved quality service also makes the firm more competitive. High service quality is achieved by knowing operational process through identifying problems in service and defining measures for service performances and outcomes as well as level of customer satisfaction. Zeitham (1981), has stated that customers of hospitality often blame themselves when dissatisfied for their bad choice. Employee must be aware that dissatisfied customers may not complain and therefore the employees should seek out sources of dissatisfaction and resolve them. Customer satisfaction, service reliability and service constituency are used here as indicators of service quality.

Customer Satisfaction: Customer satisfaction is a psychological state resulting from comparing perceived performance with expectations of an individual after consumption of a product or service (Richard, 1980). Customer satisfaction is the extent to which a product's perceived performance matches a buyer's expectations (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Customer satisfaction is a post-consumption evaluative judgment concerning a specific product or service, and it reflects a comparison of its perceived performance with expectations (Zeithaml et al., 1993). Customer satisfaction is an individual's emotional response to the

perceived outcome of a consumption experience with a product or service (Westbrook & Oliver, 1991). Customer satisfaction is the overall evaluation of a product or service experience, reflecting a consumer's cognitive appraisal of its features and benefits (Fornell, 1992).

Service Reliability: Service reliability is the ability of a system or service to consistently deliver its intended functionality and performance under varying conditions (Heidemann & Touch, 2005). Service reliability refers to the extent to which a service consistently meets or exceeds its users' expectations, regardless of external factors (Komi-Sirviö, 2008). Service reliability encompasses the ability of a service or system to function correctly, without failures or errors, even when subjected to varying workloads and stresses (Reiser & Bertrand, 1980). Service reliability is the degree to which a service consistently performs its intended function with minimal downtime and minimal negative impact on users (Malek & Medvidović, 2000).

Service Consistency: Service consistency refers to the degree to which a service provider maintains uniformity and reliability in delivering its services over time (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Service consistency is the ability of a service provider to meet customer expectations in a dependable and predictable manner across various interactions and touchpoints (Fitzsimmons & Fitzsimmons, 2006). Service consistency involves delivering services with a high level of reliability, stability, and uniformity to build trust and confidence among customers (Johnston & Clark, 2005).

Transformational Leadership Style and Service Quality

According to Bass (1985), theory of two different types of leadership, transformational leaders encourage subordinates to focus on common goal, missions and visions rather than personal interests; this often results in employee performance effectiveness. In addition, transformational leadership style can improve group cohesiveness, commitment, motivation and performance (Ali, et al., 2015; Schaubroeck et al., 2016). Employees are stimulated to focus attention on the group and organisation as they work to achieve their goals (Breevaart et al., 2016). Providing good service quality is viewed as vitally important in terms of satisfying and retaining customers (Huo-Tsan Chang et al., 2019). Many recent studies have opined that transformational leadership positively related to service quality (Schmitt et al., 2016; Schaubroeck et al., 2016; Breevaart et al., 2014; Cheng et al., 2013; Ali et al., 2015). Based on these studies, transformational leaders have been associated with the characteristics of inspirational motivation, idealized influence (Charisma), intellectual stimulation (innovation) and individualized consideration (mentoring and coaching).

Many researchers had interest in studying transformational style. The study reviewed that leadership literature which stressed on the assessment of transformational leadership (Bass, 1997) and employee commitment to service quality. Avolio and Bass (2002), advocated transformational leadership as the most sensitive style to developing a shared vision of a more desirable work culture. They further indicate that transformational style is more conducive to employee commitment to service quality. As a result, the likelihood that employees will adopt the managers orientation to service quality increases. Furthermore, transformational leaders provide their employees with a vision and transmit a common goal regarding the importance of service quality and also show them consideration and stimulate them in their work. In other words, service quality is increased under transformational leadership. Some researchers have suggested that intellectual stimulation (innovation) behaviour directly leads to service quality (Yanget et al., 2016; Santos-Vijande et al., 2016; Sok & Danaher, 2018). while others purport that job standardisation leads to greater customer awareness, which increases service quality (Kasiri et al., 2017; Chen & Lin, 2015; Tsaur, Wang et al., 2014). Having considered these findings in empirical researches, this study hypothesizes the relationship between transformational leadership and service quality for further enquiries as follows:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria.

Theoretical Review

The study was mainly anchored on Social Exchange Theory. The justification for the adoption of Social Exchange Theory as the theoretical foundation of this work titled: 'leadership style and organisational performance', is predicated on the relevance of this theory to the independent and dependent variables. The theory explains that workers and management have their own unique expectations in their contractual relationship and that the extent to which these expectations are met will influence or determine the quality of relationship. Employers expect employees to show unwavering commitment towards the achievement of goals and targets by making meaningful inputs. On the other end, the employee expects his employer to provide an enabling working condition and adapt fair leadership style that will guarantee meeting their social aspirations at work. This theory posits that the extent to which management is able to provide an enabling environment for employee to be satisfied with their jobs will influence his degree of willingness, enthusiasm, and dedication towards continuing to work enthusiastically for the organisation.

2.3 Empirical Review

Aghahowa (2021), examined the leadership styles and its impact on organisational performance in Guinness Nigeria Plc, Benin City, Edo State of Nigeria. The sample size of 35 was adopted, using Taro Yamane formula. Data collected were analysed using frequency and graphs. The study revealed that leadership styles significantly influence organisational performance of Guinness Nigeria Plc, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. From the study, it was concluded that leadership styles have both positive and negative impacts on organisational performance.

AbdulRahman et al, (2021) examined the influence of transformational leadership on organisational performance: A case study in Indonesia. This was performed on 400 respondents, encompassing employees from the national agency of drug and food control in Indonesia. The research model adopted was validated using structural equation modeling technique with Amos tool.. The findings showed transformational leadership as a significant predictor of readiness to change and it proved relevant in empowering knowledge sharing quality, which in turn affects organisational performance.

Ekpenyong (2020) examined the impact of leadership style on employees' performance in a business organisation: A case study of Guarantee Trust Bank PLC, Abuja. . The Regression analysis was used for test of hypotheses. It was found that there is no significant relationship between the leadership style a bank manager adopts and employee's performance. The regression analysis showed there is no significant impact between leadership style especially transformational leadership on the staff performance.

Joyce et al. (2018) investigated leadership style and its impact on employee performance in Klang Valley. A sample size of two hundred and fifty (250) respondents was used using non-probability convenient sampling method. Regression analysis was conducted to analyse the data. The result shows that autocratic and democratic leadership style has positive and significant impact on employee performance. However, we found that laissez-fair leadership style have no significant influence on employee performance.

Ademola (2020) examined leadership styles and its impact on employee performance of Chi Limited in Lagos Nigeria. This study population that the researcher had to conduct the study was 2500 employees of Chi Limited located in Lagos, Nigeria. The researcher sent the survey to a sample of 334 respondents, drawn randomly from a pool of 2500 Chi limited staff which was acquired through the human resource department. PPCM was coded and inputted into SPSS for analysis. The findings show that transformational has a significant and positive correlation with employee performance.

Koech and Namusonge (2012), investigated the effect of leadership styles on organisational performance at state-owned corporations in Kenya. A descriptive survey research based on the perceptions of middle and senior managers in thirty (30) state owned corporations based in Mombasa, Kenya was undertaken. A structured self-completed research questionnaire was thereafter distributed and collected after one week. The completed questionnaires were checked for plausibility, integrity and completeness resulting in seventy-two (72) usable cases. To discover the leadership styles that influence organisational performance, correlation analysis was employed using descriptive and inferential statistical measures. Correlations between the transformational leadership factors and organisational performance. Based on

findings, the study concluded that transformational leadership style has a strong positive correlation with organisational performance.

Sadia (2018), investigated the impact of transformational leadership style on organisational performance of manufacturing sector in Pakistan. The data collected were analyzed using figures, tables, graphs, and frequency. Findings of the study revealed that transformational leadership style has statistical and economically impact on organisational performance. From the research findings, it was suggested that the managers should be provided with training on how to encourage and recognize both diversity and individuality in a group.

Ebrahim, (2018), examined the impact of leadership styles on organisational performance. The data were collected using the survey questionnaire. The reliability of the data was measured using Cronbach's Alpha reliability co-efficient. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient values for charismatic leadership, bureaucratic leadership. From the results revealed that transformational leadership and autocratic leadership styles have a positive relationship with the organisational performance

Makambe and Gaone (2020) examined the effects of leadership styles on employee's performance of a selected commercial bank in Botswana. The study population comprised 433 employees from which a sample of 200 was randomly selected. Data was analyzed through the factor analysis, regression analysis and analysis of variance. The results of the study revealed that there was a significant utilization of transformational on employee's performance at the selected commercial banks in Botswana.

METHODOLOGY

The explanatory cross sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in South-west Nigeria, specifically, Lagos, Ondo, Ekiti, Oyo, Osun and Ogun states. The population of the study consisted of twenty-seven (27) telecommunication companies' headquarters operating in South West region of Nigeria (Lagos, Ondo, Ekiti, Oyo, Osun and Ogun) Census sampling research was employed using the entire population of Twenty-Seven (27) Telecommunication Companies since it was deemed manageable for coverage. Five (5) knowledgeable managers were conveniently selected from each company to respond to a questionnaire on behalf of their organization. These managers included positions such as Human Resource Managers, ICT Managers, Marketing Managers, Customer Relation Managers, and Research/Development Managers, contributing to a total of One Hundred and Thirty-Five (135) respondents. Primary data was collected by administering a questionnaire with a 4-point Likert scale to these relevant managers across the Twenty-Seven (27) Telecommunication Companies in the South West region of Nigeria. Out of the one hundred and thirty-five (135) questionnaires distributed, one hundred and eight (108) copies were successfully retrieved, representing an 80% response rate. For data analysis, both descriptive and bivariate analyses were conducted using Spearman rank order correlation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 (see Appendix) discussed the demographic about respondents The gender distributions table presented above shows that seventy (70) representing 65% of the total respondents were male, while the total number of female respondents was thirty-eight (38) representing 35% of the entire respondents. The age distribution data presented above shows that thirty-four (34) representing 32% of the respondents fall under the age group of 18-30years. Fifty-three representing 49% fall under the age bracket of 31-40 years. While twenty-one (21) representing 19% of the respondents fall under the age group of 41 years and above. This implies that Telecommunication Companies headquarters operating in South West region of Nigeria have more of office managers who are within the age bracket of 31-40 years. The educational qualification status distribution presented above shows that 51 representing 54% of the respondents have with first degree certificate, 33 respondents representing 35% have M.Sc certificate, while 11 respondents representing 11% have PhD certificate

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

S/N	Items	Responses				Total	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. D	Remarks
		SA	A	D	SD						
TLS 1	Leaders in my company believes in development of employees by inspiring and motivating them.	59	20	18	11	108	1.00	4.00	3.883	0.971	Agree
TLS 2	Leaders in my company influences us ideally to be best of ourselves.	62	24	16	6	108	1.00	4.00	4.301	1.075	Agree
TLS 3	We are being motivated always by our superiors, which is helping to drive the growth of this company.	58	23	15	12	108	1.00	4.00	4.029	1.007	Agree
TLS 4	The fact that our leaders help us to develop our skills has helped in enhancing our creativity in thinking out new approaches to do things.	48	37	15	8	108	1.00	4.00	4.009	1.002	Agree
Weighted Value									4.055	1.013	Agree

Source: Survey Data, 2024 (SPSS V. 22.0)

Table 2 above reveals mean scores up to 4 points across all the response items apart from item 1. Item 1 with a mean score of 3.883 implies that the respondents believed strongly that leaders in their company believes in development of employees by inspiring and motivating them. Item 2 with a mean score of 4.301 implies that the respondents are of the view that leaders in their company influences them ideally to be best of themselves. Item 3 with a mean score of 4.029 indicates that the respondents affirmed that they are being motivated always by their superiors, which is helping to drive the growth of their company. Item 4 with the mean score of 4.009 indicates that the fact that their leaders help them to develop their skills has helped in enhancing their creativity in thinking out new approaches to do things. From all indication above, it is obvious that managers in telecommunication companies under study adopt more of transformational leadership style. The closeness in the standard deviation shows that respondents are homogenous in their view.

Bivariate Analysis Results

Table 3: Correlations of Transformational Leadership Style and Service Quality

		Transformational Leadership Style	Service Quality
Transformational Leadership Style	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.667**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
Spearman's rho	N	108	108
	Correlation Coefficient	.667**	1.000
Service Quality	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	108	108

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2024 (SPSS V. 22.0)

Table 3 shows r value of 0.667 at a significance level of 0.00 which is less than the chosen alpha level of 0.05 for the hypothesis relating transformational leadership style and service quality. Since the significance value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) which states that there is no significant relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria was rejected and the alternate hypothesis (H_{a1})

was accepted. This implies that there is a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the above results, the study revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership style and service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria; This implies that adequate adoption of transformational leadership style in terms of inspiration vision, idealized influence, individual consideration and intellectual stimulation brings about a corresponding improvement of organisational performance measured by service quality. The finding was in tandem with Yukl (2014) who found that transformational leadership can lead to positive changes in followers that could serve as models for future leaders. Yukl (2014) found that transformational leadership also appeals to the employees' moral values. People's awareness and motivation to effect change in institutions will rise as a result of this as well. Leaders who use transformational leadership will gain the respect and loyalty of their followers. Leaders who are transformational inspire their followers to go above and beyond their initial expectations this necessitates employee motivation in terms of job security (employee job competence and task significance), promotion (vertical promotion and horizontal promotion) and recognition (award and incentives). When it comes to inspiring employee motivation and articulating an inspiring vision, transformational leadership involves internalization (Yukl (2014)). Other than that, transformational leadership inspires their followers, and as a result, their followers tend to imitate and espouse their leaders' attributes.

In line with the above findings, Breevaart et al. (2016) found that transformational leaders encourage subordinates to focus on common goal, missions and visions rather than personal interests; this often results in employee performance effectiveness. They further indicate that transformational style is more conducive to employee commitment to service quality. Likely, Alsamydai and Alensour (2016) found that transformational leaders provide their employees with a vision and transmit a common goal regarding the importance of service quality. Effective implementation of transformational leadership style as the enterprises developed, grew and matured. Ethelmary and Anthony (2020) revealed that effective implementation of transformational leadership style has the potentials of market share the life of organisations in the face of stiff competition in meeting their desired performance in term of service quality.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis, the study concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership style and organisational performance (in terms of service quality of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria). Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made: Management of Telecommunication Companies in South West, Nigeria should ensure the effective implementation of leadership style that has the potentials of improving service quality, profitability and market share as the life of organisation in the face of stiff competition in meeting its desired performance. Management of Telecommunication Companies should adopt visionary approach where managers are optimistic and persistent, in order to encourage employees towards better job performance.

The study extends the frontiers of knowledge on how as transformational leadership style (inspiration vision, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence and individual consideration), interacts with organisational performance is measured in the current work in terms of service quality (customer satisfaction, service reliability and service consistency). The researcher confronted limitation, among others, the researcher was unable to retrieve all of the distributed copies of questionnaire. This limited the researcher to cover only telecommunication companies operating in South West, Nigeria. This study suggested that similar study should be conducted to cover wider geographical scope like two geo-political zone in Nigeria

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Table 1: Demographic Analysis

Characteristics	Options	N	%
Gender	Male	70	65
	Female	38	35
	Total	108	100
Age Group	18-30 Years	34	32.0
	31-40 Years	53	49.0
	41 Years and above	21	19.0
	Total	108	100.0
Position within the Public Sector	First Degree	51	54.0
	MSc	33	35.0
	PhD	11	11.0
	Total	108	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025